

Influence of renal dysfunction phenotype on mortality in decompensated heart failure with preserved and mid-range ejection fraction

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Abstract

Background

Natriuretic peptides or the blood urea nitrogen to creatinine ratio (BUN/creat) can identify high- vs low-risk renal impairment (RI) in patients with heart failure and reduced ejection fraction (HF-REF). However, the situation in HF patients with preserved ejection fraction (HF-PEF) and mid-range ejection fraction (HF-MREF) remains unclear.

Methods

We evaluated patients from the Spanish National Registry of Heart Failure (RICA) that were admitted to Internal Medicine units with acute decompensated HF. Median admission values were used to define elevated NT-proBNP and BUN/creat.

Results

A total of 935 patients were evaluated, 743 with HF-PEF and 192 with HF-MREF). In patients with both NT-proBNP and BUN/creat below median admission values, RI was not associated with mortality (HR 1.15; 95% CI 0.7–1.87, $p=0.581$ in HF-PEF

and HR 1.27; 95% CI 0.58–2.81, $p=0.548$ in HF-MREF). However, in patients with both elevated NT-proBNP and BUN/creat, those with RI had worse survival than those without RI (HR 2.01, 95% CI 1.33–3.06, $p<0.001$ in HF-PEF and HR 2.79, 95% CI 1.37–5.67, $p=0.005$ in HF-MREF). In HF-PEF even patients with RI with only 1 of the 2 parameters elevated, had a substantially higher risk of death compared to patients without RI (HR 1.53; 95% CI 1.04 to 2.26; $p=0.031$).

Conclusions

In this clinical cohort of acute decompensated HF-PEF and HF-MREF patients, the combined use of NT-proBNP and BUN/creat stratifies patients with RI into groups with significantly different prognoses.

Keywords

1. [Renal dysfunction](#)
2. [NT-proBNP](#)
3. [Blood urea nitrogen to creatinine ratio](#)
4. [Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction](#)
5. [Heart failure with mid-range ejection fraction](#)